

Live Coding Dynamical Systems

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Abstract

We present a method for live coding dynamical systems (LCDS), mathematical equations for complex, self regulating systems ubiquitous in science and engineering. Live coding dynamical systems provides opportunities for students to learn dynamical systems in a fun and creative way, create striking visual effects, explore unconventional dynamical systems such as those over tori, and introduce novel challenges for performative live coding.

1 Introduction

Dynamical systems theory provides a mathematical framework for describing and understanding the behavior of complex, self regulating systems across a variety of fields, including ecology, epidemiology, and chemistry. A dynamical system consists of a set of n variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n which evolve over time, along with a set of rules dictating how the variables' current values effect their future values. These rules are often encoded as a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs):

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt} x_1(t) &= f_1(t, x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t)) \\ \frac{d}{dt} x_2(t) &= f_2(t, x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t)) \\ &\dots \\ \frac{d}{dt} x_n(t) &= f_n(t, x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t))\end{aligned}$$

where $\frac{d}{dt} x_i(t)$ is the derivative of x_i with respect to time at time t .

The set of values which the variables can take is known as the *state space* of the system. The majority of literature on dynamical systems focuses on those with the real numbers \mathbb{R} as their state space. As we shall see, live coding visuals with dynamical systems enables us to work over other interesting state spaces such as tori.

Strogatz 2018 offers a thorough and mathematically rigorous introduction to dynamical systems.

This paper describes methods for live coding visuals, whereby systems of particles change color and move around a screen according to dynamical systems. We describe and provide visual examples of three types of systems:

- Dynamical systems on Red-Green-Blue (RGB) color space, where the color of a particle changes based on its current color. This space can be mapped to the three dimensional torus S^3 .
- Dynamical systems on screen space, where the position of a particle on the screen changes based on its current position. This space can be encoded as a number of different mathematical objects, including the real numbers in three dimensions \mathbb{R}^3 and the three dimensional torus S^3 . We can also explore systems ubiquitous in physics where both particles' positions and velocities update dynamically.
- Dynamical systems that incorporate feedback between a particle's position, velocity, and color.

2 Related Work

This paper adds to a growing literature connecting mathematics and live coding, which offer a toolkit for educators, researchers, and performers. Eldridge 2007 studies adaptive dynamical systems such as neural oscillators

Figure 1: Particles initially arranged as two images merged together (left), an image mapped onto a torus (center), and an abstract geometrical figure (right).

and cellular automata in the context of live generative music. Recent work has explored incorporating machine learning into live coding, reviewed in Xambó 2021. Shimizu, Fiebrink, et al. 2023 offers a tool for visualizing mathematical parameters in generative music models.

This paper extends work by the author studying dynamical systems as tools for visual animation of images. Whereas Maltzman 2023 studies systems over 8-bit Red-Green-Blue color space, here we consider floating point colors, which are typically employed in shaders.

3 Methods: OpenFrameworks and Compute Shaders

We render visuals with OpenFrameworks (OF), an open source C++ based creative coding library. The three central functions of an OF application are `setup()`, `update()`, and `draw()`. `Setup()` is called to initialize variables before anything is drawn to the screen, and `update()` and `draw()` are repeatedly called to update variables and draw objects to the screen, respectively.

In `setup()`, we create a system of particles, which each have a position, velocity, and color. We can arrange these particles in a variety of ways, such as a torus, image, or abstract geometry, and either draw them as points or connect them via lines or triangles (Figure 1). The data for the particles is then stored on the graphics processing unit (GPU), so that they can be read and written to in parallel.

In `update()`, we repeatedly load a file for a compute shader. Compute shaders are programs that perform computations in parallel on the GPU. In the compute shader we can edit dynamical systems in real time to update the position, velocity, and color of all the particles.

A code example for the system described in section 6 is provided in the appendix.

4 Dynamical Systems on Color Space

We encode a particle's color at a time t as a tuple $c(t) = (r(t), g(t), b(t))$, where $r(t)$, $g(t)$, and $b(t)$ are the red, green, and blue channels of the particle's color, each taking floating point values between 0 and 1. We define a dynamical system on color space as a function f for the change in color with respect to time:

$$\frac{d}{dt} c(t) = f(c(t), t)$$

For a small increment in time Δt , the particle's color updates at time $(t + \Delta t)$ to

$$c(t + \Delta t) = (c(t) + \frac{d}{dt} c(t) \Delta t) \bmod 1$$

where `mod 1` wraps the color's value around 1, so for example 1.01 becomes .01. Alternatively we can clamp values at 0 and 1, but wrapping around allows for more dynamism. This also endows color space with a

structure equivalent to S^3 , a three dimensional torus embedded in the four dimensional space of real numbers \mathbb{R}^4 .

To see this, let us first consider a one dimensional color space, solely consisting of a red channel. We can visualize this space as a line segment spanning the interval from 0 to 1, where the left endpoint is entirely black and the right endpoint is entirely red. Note, however, that $.99 + .02 = .01 \pmod 1$, meaning that when we increase in value from near the right endpoint we should end up back at the left endpoint. We can visually represent this by gluing both points together to form a circle (Figure 2).

Now consider a color space with red and green values, which we can depict as a square of width and height 1. Similarly, we can glue both endpoints on the bottom and top edge to form a cylinder, and then glue both edges of the cylinder to form a torus. Since this is a two-dimensional surface, we require three dimensions to visualize it.

We can try to do the same thing with a color space that includes red, green, and blue, which we can initially depict as a cube. If we glue together each pair of faces of the cube, we will get a three dimensional surface, embedded in four dimensional space. While we cannot visualize a four dimensional object, we can consider its three dimensional cross sections. Just as the cross sections of a cube are squares, and the cross sections of a 2-torus are circles, the cross sections of a 3-torus are 2-tori, depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Representing color space as a circle in one dimension and a torus in two dimensions.

Figure 3: Three cross sections of RGB color space at different blue values.

An example of a dynamical system over color space, involving feedback between each color, is

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt} r(t) &= .1 \\ \frac{d}{dt} g(t) &= .01r(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt} b(t) &= g(t) \sin(t - r(t)).\end{aligned}$$

which is visually depicted in figure 4.

5 Dynamical Systems on Screen Space

We encode a particle's position as a tuple $p(t) = (x(t), y(t), z(t))$. Similarly to the previous section, we update the position dynamically as

$$\frac{d}{dt} p(t) = f(p(t), t)$$

where the particle's new position becomes

$$p(t + \Delta t) = p(t) + \Delta t \frac{d}{dt} p(t).$$

We can alternatively wrap the particle's position around the dimensions of the screen, with the update rule

$$p(t + \Delta t) = \begin{bmatrix} x(t) + \Delta t \frac{d}{dt} x(t) \bmod W \\ y(t) + \Delta t \frac{d}{dt} y(t) \bmod H \\ [(z(t) + \Delta t \frac{d}{dt} z(t) \bmod Z) - 2Z] \end{bmatrix}$$

where W and H are the width and height of the screen, respectively, and Z some value chosen to constrain the z -component of the particle's position. This endows the state space of our system with a mapping to S^3 , similarly to the previous section.

An example is the famous Lorenz system, a model of atmospheric convection which, with the following choice of parameters, exhibits chaos, meaning that particles which start close to each other will rapidly diverge over time:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt} x(t) &= 10(y - x) \\ \frac{d}{dt} y(t) &= x(28 - z) - y \\ \frac{d}{dt} z(t) &= xy - \frac{8}{3}z.\end{aligned}$$

We can also live code dynamical systems on the particle's velocity $v(t) = (v_x(t), v_y(t), v_z(t)) = (\frac{d}{dt} x(t), \frac{d}{dt} y(t), \frac{d}{dt} z(t))$,

where

$$\frac{d}{dt} v(t) = f(v(t), p(t), t).$$

Thus a particle's velocity and therefore its position change based on its current velocity and position.

Figure 4: Top: Original configuration of a particle system as two images merged together. Evolution of the particles over time according to the dynamical systems described in sections 4 (Left), 5 (center), and 6 (Right).

6 Feedback Systems

We have discussed nine dimensions along which a particle can evolve dynamically. Each of these dimensions can interact with each other, introducing a plethora of visual effects which can be achieved by developing and combining various dynamical systems.

The following system¹ exhibits feedback between a particle's position, velocity, and color, resulting in a striking visual with a bizarre symmetry (Figure 4):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} v_x(t) &= v_x(t) - 10\hat{x}(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt} v_y(t) &= v_y(t) - 10(g(t) - r(t))\hat{y}(t)z(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt} v_z(t) &= v_z(t)v_x(t) + (v_x(t))^2 - 100\left(\frac{r(t)}{g(t)}\right) \\ \frac{d}{dt} p(t) &= v(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt} r(t) &= .01\left(\frac{x(t)}{v_x(t)}\right) \\ \frac{d}{dt} g(t) &= -.01\frac{v_y(t)}{v_x(t)} \\ \frac{d}{dt} b(t) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

7 Discussion

Live coding dynamical systems pose unique challenges for performances. One challenge is ensuring that the system being implemented preserves the qualitative structure of particles both in color space and screen space. For example, consider the following system over color space with the parameter k :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} r(t) &= kr(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt} g(t) &= (g(t))^2 \\ \frac{d}{dt} b(t) &= .01 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 7 depicts an image evolving according to this system with both $k = 2$ and $k = 1$. When $k = 1$, the red values of all pixels converges to 0, so the image loses some of its textural features.

Similarly, consider the following systems over screen space, which is a slight adaptation of the well known chaotic Rossler attractor described in Rössler 1967:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} x(t) &= -\hat{y} - z \\ \frac{d}{dt} y(t) &= \hat{x} + .2 * \hat{y} \\ \frac{d}{dt} z(t) &= .2 + z * (\hat{x} - 5.7). \end{aligned}$$

We wrap coordinates around the screen as described in section 5, setting $Z = 10$. Also consider a modified version of this system, where we set $Z = 100$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} x(t) &= -\sin(y) * \hat{x} - z \\ \frac{d}{dt} y(t) &= .01 * \hat{y} * \sin(x) \\ \frac{d}{dt} z(t) &= .2 + z * (\hat{x} - 5.7). \end{aligned}$$

Figure 6 depicts a particle structure evolving according to both systems. Whereas the first system mostly preserves the structure and causes it move in an elegant spiral, the second causes it to decohere. This can be seen as an opportunity as well as a challenge, as some might find the decoherence visually appealing due to its ephemerality.

Thus, LCDS pose the unique challenge of permanent information loss. The system we just described causes the structure to decohere, but we cannot find a dynamical system that will return us to the original structure.

In contrast, consider live coding a fragment shader, where one would typically map each point on the screen to a color. Say we begin with a shader that creates a nice looking visual, and then when we edit the code we don't like the resulting visual. We can simply undo the changes we made to the code to revert to the original visual.

¹. Note that $\hat{x} = x - \frac{W}{2}$, and $\hat{y} = y - \frac{H}{2}$, where W and H are the width and height of the screen, respectively.

Figure 5: Image (top) evolving according to a dynamical system over color space described in section 7, with $k = 2$ (left) and $k = 1$ (right). Note that when $k = 1$ the image loses its red components.

Figure 6: Particle structure (top) evolving according to the Rossler attractor with (left) and without (right) modifications.

Thus, a performer live coding dynamical systems must be wary that a system could cause particles' colors to disappear, or their positions to lose their original structure by flying off the screen or converging to a single area. When live coding a dynamical system, we suggest beginning with an extremely small timestep to prevent drastic changes in color and position, and gradually increasing the timestep if the system results in a favorable visual.

Identifying dynamical systems that generate striking visual effects offers a fruitful direction for collaboration between mathematicians and visual artists. Most dynamical systems research and dynamical systems courses concern systems over the real numbers, while those explored in this paper also incorporate systems over tori.

There are a number of ways in which LCDS can facilitate interactive performances. Data from sensors, music, or cameras that are modulated by the audience or performers can tune parameters to dynamical systems. An example is *Windchime*, an audio-visual installation interfacing weather data with a particle system, described in BEYLS 2014.

Dynamical systems are often used to study synchronization, including in neurons and fireflies. A potential challenge is to have multiple performers live coding dynamical systems simultaneously and synchronize their systems. The performers can take turns as leaders and followers, attempting to guide their particles to follow each other.

Dynamical systems can also be incorporated into existing frameworks bridging live coding and choreography, for example Sicchio 2014. Dancers can respond to particles moving according to dynamical systems, or live coders can attempt to design systems that compliment the dancers' movements. Another opportunity is translating dynamical systems to choreographic scores.

LCDS can serve as an exciting entryway for students being introduced to dynamical systems and differential equations, with the added benefit that they can learn about graphics programming along the way. A potential exercise could be challenging students to come up with dynamical systems that exhibit specific behaviors such as being bounded in specific areas, exhibiting oscillations, or cycling between particular colors.

Dynamical systems offer an exciting frontier of exploration for the live coding community, with a potential plethora of combinations of visual effects.

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A Appendix

For an understanding of OpenFrameworks applications see Noble 2009, and for a tutorial on compute shaders in OpenFrameworks see Matyka 2022. We include the main files of an OF application, as well as the compute shader, in a github repository: <https://github.com/ymaltsman/LCDS>.